

ClairCity - Citizen Led Air pollution Reduction in Cities

D1.11 Project Advisory Board membership established

October 2016 (*Revised in July 2017*)

Contents

Document Details.....	3
Overview of the External Advisory Board (EAB)	4

Document Details

Authors	Irati Artola (Trinomics)
Document description	<p>This document materialises the 'establishment' of the External Advisory Board (EAB) providing an overview document of its final members.</p> <p>The members of the EAB received upfront a Terms of Reference (ToR) that explained the involvement and activities expected from them. The majority of the experts we contacted agreed to be part of it.</p> <p>WP1 lead, Trinomics, has collected the signed letters of each of the members accepting the ToR (not included in this deliverable since they include personal information such as address and telephone numbers).</p>

Overview of the External Advisory Board (EAB)

The following table illustrates the composition of the first ClairCity External Advisory Board (EAB). These twelve people have already confirmed their participation in the ClairCity EAB and have agreed to the Terms of Reference (ToR) (signed letters are enclosed at the end of this document).

Table -1 External Advisory Board members

Name	Country	Organisation & Role	Expertise relevant to CLAIR City
EU Advisory Board Members			
1) Olav Peeters	Belgium	Scientific Coordinator at Belgian Interregional Environment Agency (IRCEL - CELINE)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Air quality data (e-)reporting - Harmonisation, comparability of air quality measuring - Real-time information exchange, sensors
2) Anette Persson	Sweden	Senior adviser at Swedish Ministry of the Environment and Energy - Swedish Energy Agency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Acquainted with ClairCity (involved during the bid) - Engagement of citizens, social practice theory
3) Harold Wilhite	Oslo	Research Director at the University of Oslo's Centre for Development and Environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Prominent name in social practice theory - Interest in air quality and CO₂ - Experience working on EU and non EU countries
4) Dimosthenis Sarigiannis	Greece	Project Lead ICARUS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Maximising synergies between ClairCity and ICARUS
5) Francesco Pilla	Ireland	Project Lead i-Scape	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Maximising synergies between ClairCity and i-Scape - Italian - Urban design perspective
6) Sandor Nagy	Hungary	Vice Mayor for Urban Development of the CIVITAS programme	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Eastern European coverage - Air quality - Policies and governance
7) Anna Dworakowska	Poland	Krakow Smog Alert	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Eastern Europe coverage - NGO close to the work of cities - Air quality - Impacts of heating, cooling, etc.
8) Chris Dunford	UK	Sustainability Engagement Manager at At-Bristol Science Centre	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public engagement - Science communication - Conduit to data visualization experts
International Advisory Board Members			
9) Jon Bickel	Peru	Swisscontact Country Manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - South American coverage - Air quality, climate change
10) Roseanne Diab	South Africa	Executive Officer of the Academy of Science of South Africa (ASSAf)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - African coverage (based in Durban) - Well positioned to help dissemination in Africa, including young people - Air quality and CO₂ - Often in Europe through her work for IPCC

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 689289

11) Mukesh Khare	India	Indian Institute of Technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Asian coverage (based in Delhi)- Air quality, CO₂- Data / modelling expertise- Policies
12) Glynda Bathan	Philipinnes	Deputy Executive Director at Clean Air Asia	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Asian coverage- Lawyer, environmental policy, environmental management- Experience assisting cities with policies and roadmaps

As proof of the commitment of the above listed EAB members to participating as ClairCity's advisors and engage in dissemination, we have collected signed letters. Since these letters contain personal information, we will not make attach the letters publicly available.